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**EFFECT OF BODY MASS INDEX ON THE
PREVALENCE OF SCIATICA**

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ABSTRACT:

Sciatica is a condition in which pain radiates down the leg from the lower back. The pain could radiate down the back, outside, or front of the leg. The onset is typically abrupt after tasks such as heavy lifting, but it may also be incremental. This cross-sectional research was conducted among patients who presented to various hospitals' outdoor departments. On a predefined proforma, names, ages, genders, symptoms, BMI, and the presence of sciatica were reported. SPSS Ver. 23.0 was used to enter and analyze all the data. A total of 90 patients were included in this study. There were 45 males (50%) and 45 females (50%). The mean BMI of the patients was 24.566 ± 3.45 , the minimum was 19.23 and the maximum was 28.54 kg/m². The mean age of the patients was 45.56 ± 4.45 years. Out of 90 patients, fourteen patients presented with sciatica and it was strongly associated with higher BMI.

KEYWORD: BMI, SCIATICA

INTRODUCTION:

Sciatica is a condition in which pain radiates down the leg from the lower back. The pain could radiate down the back, outside, or front of the leg. The onset is typically abrupt after tasks such as heavy lifting, but it may also be incremental. The discomfort is often characterized as shooting. Symptoms typically involve only one side of the body. Certain triggers, on the other hand, can cause pain on both sides. Back pain in the lower back is normal. Various parts of the affected leg and foot can experience weakness or numbness (1). The word "sciatica" refers to a symptom—pain along the sciatic nerve pathway—rather than a disorder, illness, or disease. Some people use it to describe any pain that begins in the lower back and moves down the leg. The pain is usually characterized as shooting or shock-like, and it moves quickly along the affected nerves' path. Others use the term to describe nerve dysfunction caused by compression of one or more lumbar or sacral nerve roots because of a spinal disc herniation. Pain generally occurs in the dermatome's distribution, which extends from below the knee to the foot. It is likely that it's related to neurological disorders like numbness and fatigue (2). The compression of the lumbar nerves L4 or L5 or the sacral nerve S1 is the most common cause of sciatica. Sciatica may also be caused by compression of the sacral nerves S2 or S3 or the sciatic nerve itself. A spinal disc bulge or herniation is the most common cause of sciatica in 90% of cases. An outer annulus fibrosus and an inner nucleus pulposus make up intervertebral spinal discs. Early in human growth, the annulus fibrosus forms a rigid ring around the nucleus pulposus, trapping the nucleus pulposus' gelatinous contents within the disc. Discs divide the vertebrae in the spine, improving spinal flexibility and allowing nerve roots to exit the spinal cord properly into the gaps between the vertebrae. The annulus fibrosus weakens and becomes less rigid with age, making it more susceptible to tear. The nucleus pulposus can extrude through a tear in the annulus fibrosus and press against spinal nerves inside the spinal cord, cauda equina, or exiting nerve roots, causing inflammation, numbness, or unbearable pain.

Facet syndrome, which is characterized by lower back pain and referred pain in the posterior thigh, is caused by inflammation of spinal tissue spreading to adjacent facet joints (3,4). The roughening, enlarging, or misalignment (spondylolisthesis) of vertebrae, or disc degeneration that decreases the diameter of the lateral foramen from which nerve roots exit the spine, are other causes of sciatica secondary to spinal nerve entrapment. If sciatica is caused by compression of a dorsal nerve root and is followed by an inflammatory response, it is referred to as lumbar radiculopathy or radiculitis. Compression of peripheral parts of the sciatic nerve, normally caused by soft tissue stress in the piriformis or associated muscles, can also cause sciatica-like pain in the buttocks (5,6).

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This cross-sectional research was conducted among patients who presented to various hospitals' outdoor departments. On a predefined proforma, names, ages, genders, symptoms, BMI, and the presence of sciatica were reported. SPSS Ver. 23.0 was used to enter and analyze all the data. The mean and standard deviation of the quantitative variables were presented. The frequency and percentages were used to present the qualitative variables.

RESULTS:

A total of 90 patients were included in this study. There were 45 males (50%) and 45 females (50%). The mean BMI of the patients was 24.566 ± 3.45 , the minimum was 19.23 and the maximum was 28.54 kg/m². The mean age of the patients was 45.56 ± 4.45 years. Out of 90 patients, fourteen patients presented with sciatica and it was strongly associated with higher BMI.

DISCUSSION:

The most popular approaches for diagnosing sciatica are taking a medical history and conducting a physical examination. Patients complain of leg pain that radiates. They may be asked to explain the pain's distribution and whether it radiates below the knee, and sketches may be used to measure it. Sciatica is characterized by a dermatomal pattern of radiating pain. Patients can also experience sensory problems (5,6).

Neurological assessment is a major part of the physical exam. The straight leg raising measure, also known as Lasègue's sign, is the most widely used investigation. Low back pain is normal in sciatica patients, but it is generally less intense than the leg pain. The diagnostic importance of a patient's medical history and physical examination has not been extensively researched. There are no things from the past or physical examination assessments that have both a high sensitivity and accuracy. The straight leg raising test's pooled sensitivity is estimated to be 91 percent, with a pooled specificity of 26 percent. The crossed straight leg raising measure, which has a pooled specificity of 88 percent but a sensitivity of just 29 percent, is the only test with a high specificity. Overall, a diagnosis of sciatica seems warranted if a patient experiences normal radiating pain in one leg, as well as a positive outcome on one or more neurological tests showing nerve root tension or neurological deficit.

Conservative sciatica care focuses on pain relief, either by analgesics or through reducing pressure on the nerve root. Conservative therapies do not explicitly change the normal course of sciatica in most patients or reduce symptoms, according to a recent systematic review. Appropriately educating patients about the causes and predicted prognosis could be a key component of the management plan. However, there have not been any randomized controlled trials on educating patients about sciatica (7,8).

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